

PHYSICAL FITNESS IN POWERLIFTING AND ITS SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS.

Jumayev Sirojiddin

A student of the Termiz branch of the
Tashkent Medical Academy.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7310707>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26th October 2022
Accepted: 07th November 2022
Online: 10th November 2022

KEY WORDS

Powerlifting, training, bodybuilding, aesthetic, Table press.

ABSTRACT

There are many sports in sports, and if you want to develop your muscles and strength, then it will be useful and relevant to know what your strength is and how to properly address it to achieve results. It is important to know the rules of effective training. This article provides information about the sport of powerlifting.

What is Powerlifting? First, note the translation, so "power" means power and "raise" means rise. Powerlifting is a strength sport in which the main task of the athlete is to lift a large weight in the sum of three exercises. A power triathlon includes a crash, bench mat, and finger sticks. It is important to note that the main difference between powerlifting and bodybuilding is that the athlete's body structure and appearance are irrelevant.

Powerlifting - specifications. In this sport, international competitions are held in which athletes participate, and they are divided into weight categories. Powerlifting is awarded to the heavyweight athlete who wins with an equal number of triangles. According to the rules of the international federation, the following categories are divided by age:

- Boys and girls - 12-18 years old;
- Teenagers and teenagers - 19-23 years old;
- Adults - 23 years and older;
- Open age categories - over 13 years old.

Finding Ptentlifting - you need to find out what it means for women, with regular exercises, you can forget about a reasonable waist and female forms, because a person who often works with weights, not only develops his strength, but also increases muscle mass and o change is provided by ham. In addition, calorie consumption in professional training is of great importance, and this ham affects this indicator.

Powerlifting - men

You can see a lot of men in gyms working with a lot of heavy weights, but only one of them are true powerlifters. Many people confuse classic powerlifting with bodybuilding, so it is important to consider the main differences:

In the first case, the goal is to increase strength indicators, and in the second, to achieve an increase in muscle mass, taking into account aesthetic proportions. In powerlifting, it is not important whether the exercises are perfect, because the goal is to use the maximum of the muscles to

increase the weight, but in bodybuilding, this method is pure or easy. there should be a trick. Another difference should be mentioned - the complex includes basic exercises from triathlon and auxiliary exercises, but bodybuilding uses basic and isolation exercises.

How to start powerlifting?

There are several characteristics of effective training that should be taken into account in order to develop and improve the result: It is impossible to study 2-3 muscle groups for one exercise, and it is wrong to do more than three exercises for each of them. The tests involve a gradual increase in the maximum load of the platform. It's important to do a multi-set approach that can maintain technique, speed, repetitions, and weight. In training, great attention should be paid to the development of auxiliary and stabilizing muscles involved in triathlon.

Powerlifting rules include reducing body fat and increasing muscle mass. It should not be developed unilaterally, that is, all muscle groups should be loaded immediately.

Powerlifting is good and bad

With regular and proper training, you can count on the following benefits: endurance and strength, strengthening of muscles, bones and tendons, as well as the functioning of the cardiovascular system improves. Application, understanding what powerlifting is and the health benefits of this sport, it should be noted that training has a positive effect on the hormonal system, and as a result, you can use an excellent physical form. It is recommended to create a personal training program.

Injuries to powerlifting can lead to poor physical fitness, heavy weights, and incorrect exercises. Beginners are

encouraged to work with a coach to create a suitable program. If the exercises are performed incorrectly, problems of the cardiovascular system and severe injuries of ligaments, muscles, tendons and joints will increase. In addition, it is possible to change the appearance of discs and fars when lifting a large weight.

Powerlifting - Exercises

It is noted that three main exercises are used in this sport:

1. Finger benches. This is the first practice in competitions. Powerlifting for girls and men is based on the same rules. First, the panel is easily removed with a convenient handle, which is removed from the posts and located at the top of the trapezoid. The athlete separates from the witches, straightens his back, spreading his legs a little more than his shoulders.

2. Table press. In powerlifting, this exercise is performed with certain details. The athlete covers the net with a wide or medium grip. The first option is more popular, because the longer the distance between the arms, the shorter the path of the line. It is necessary to remove the stretch, lift the pelvis and keep your arms straight. The speed of the table press should be maximum, when the marble is lowered, you will shorten the shoulder blade and lower your shoulder. An important nuance is that the legs should be closer to the pelvis, and the benches are not only for the weak. The bigger the swing on the back, the shorter the deep path. parallel should be a little lower and the center of gravity should fall on the hips. The lift should be done with a flat face.

Suddenly. Powerlifting athletes perform these exercises for the last time. To take the starting position, the feet should be placed at the width of the shoulders or

more. Records are often installed in the first option. The athlete bends with a flat rope and holds the bar comfortably. Lifting the legs, the shell rises. The back should always be straight. When lifting the bar, the

hands should be straight and indifferent. Powerlifting technique takes into account that the squat can only be lowered after the knees are set and the shoulders are back.

References:

1. Vorobyov A.N. Weightlifting. - M.: "FiS", 1972.
2. Vorobyov A.N. Weightlifting. - M.: "FiS", 1988.
3. Dvorkii L.S. Weightlifting and age. - Sverdlovsk: ed. Ural. un-ta, 1989.
4. Dvorkin L.S. Heavy agletics // textbook for universities. - M., 2005.
5. Deorkii L.S. Yunsh is a weightlifter. - M.: "FiS", 1982.